

Quantitative Treatment of Variation of Specific Conductivity of Sols of Some Colloidal Dyes and Polyelectrolytes with Dilution

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Equations deduced in previous publications to account for the variation of specific conductivity of different types of colloidal electrolytes with dilution (by water) have been subjected to further test using relevant data available in the literature on benzopurpurine 4 B and its isomer prepared from meta-tolidine and also on azrehtic acid, a polyelectrolyte, extracted from the gum of the plant *Azadirachta Indica*. The equations have been found to hold good in these cases, the concentration and the corresponding specific conductivity varying over a wide range.

In previous publications¹⁻⁴ it has been shown that equations can be deduced from theoretical considerations which account quantitatively for the variation of pH and specific conductivity with dilution of a number of colloidal electrolytes. The equation for the variation of specific conductivity λ with dilution is written as follows :

$$\lambda = \theta \lambda_s + (1 - \theta) \lambda_i \quad \dots (1)$$

$$= \theta (\lambda_s - \lambda_i) + \lambda_i \quad \dots (1a)$$

In the aforesaid equations λ denotes the observed specific conductivity of the sol, containing colloidal material of concentration C (unit arbitrary), θ , the fraction per unit area of an electrode surface (of the conductivity cell) covered by the diffuse electrical double layers of the colloidal particles or macromolecules of the sol and it is equal to $C/(K_0 + C)$, K_0 being a constant, λ_s is a proportionality constant and may be interpreted to represent the specific conductivity associated with a unit area of the diffuse double layer at the plane of contact with the electrode surface and λ_i the specific conductivity of the intermicellar solution. λ_i of a highly purified sol must be very small and cannot vary much with dilution by distilled water. Its average value may, therefore, be treated as a constant.

Equation (1a) may then be expressed as follows :

$$\lambda = \theta \lambda_a + \lambda_i \quad \dots (1b)$$

where $\lambda_a = (\lambda_s - \lambda_i)$ and may be treated as a constant specially when λ_s is much greater than λ_i .

However, if λ_i is not very small and varies, even then, equation (1a) may be used in the following form, provided λ_i is determined experimentally ;

$$\lambda_m = \theta (\lambda_s - \lambda_i) \quad \dots (1c)$$

Where $\lambda_m = (\lambda - \lambda_i)$ and it represents the contribution of the micelles to the specific conductivity of the sol.

Again if some electrolyte is added to the sol so that the specific conductivity of the intermicellar solution becomes relatively high and θ is increased more and more, then correction for the increase of concentration of the electrolyte in the intermicellar solution, caused by the expulsion of the coions and their oppositely charged partner ions from the volume occupied by the colloidal particles and their double layers, has to be introduced. Equation (1) may then be written as follows :

$$\lambda = \theta \lambda_s + \lambda_i (1 - \theta) / (1 - B\theta^2) \quad \dots (2)$$

In equation (2) $\lambda_i / (1 - B\theta^2)$ represents the increase of specific conductivity of the intermicellar solution with the increase of θ and λ_i and B are constants. After some simplification, neglecting terms involving θ^3 and higher order terms equation (2) may be expressed as follows :

$$\lambda = \theta (\lambda_s - \lambda_i) + \lambda_i (1 + B\theta^2) \quad \dots (2a)$$

$$= \theta \lambda_a + \lambda_i (1 + B\theta^2) \quad \dots (2b)$$

The validity of the aforesaid equations has been tested in this paper using the data on benzopurpurine 4B and its isomer prepared from meta-tolidine and on azrehtic acid, a polyelectrolyte.

Variation of specific conductivity of the dye sols with dilution :

Robinson and Mills⁵ have investigated at 25° the variation of specific conductivity with dilution (by water) of benzopurpurine 4B and its isomer prepared from

meta-tolidine, after purifying the dyes carefully. For benzopurpurine 4B and its isomer prepared from meta-tolidine, they have used the abbreviations, the "4B dye" and the "meta-dye" respectively and the same abbreviations have been followed in this paper also. The afore-said authors⁵ have observed that 0.5 per cent solutions of the two dyes differ widely in their flocculation values for NaCl. It is also known that the 4B dye is a cotton substantive dye but the meta-dye is not (a cotton substantive dye). In the Tables 1 and 2, λ denotes the specific conductivity of the sol, λ_s the corrected specific conductivity of the ultrafiltrate which is the same as that of the intermicellar solution and $\lambda_m = (\lambda - \lambda_s)$, the specific conductivity contributed by the micelles, C denotes the concentration of the dye in gram equivalents per litre and under the heading miscellaneous are recorded the equation used and the values of the constants K_0 and λ_s .

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF SPECIFIC CONDUCTIVITY OF META-DYE SOLS WITH DILUTION

Miscellaneous	C × 10 ⁴	λ × 10 ⁶	λ _s × 10 ⁶	Values of λ _m × 10 ⁶ in recip. ohms.	
				Observed	Calculated
	145.7	1017.4	32.6	984.8	983.0
Equation used) (lc)	72.85	593.9	21.0	572.9	568.2
	36.43	317.1	13.8	303.3	308.2
	18.22	169.9	9.3	160.6	160.9
K ₀ = 405 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.554	46.39	5.39	41.0	41.6
	1.136	14.61	4.39	10.22	10.46
λ _s = 3748 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.284	6.87	4.26	2.61	2.63

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF SPECIFIC CONDUCTIVITY OF 4B DYE SOLS WITH DILUTION

Miscellaneous	C × 10 ⁴	λ × 10 ⁶	λ _s × 10 ⁶	Values of λ _m × 10 ⁶ in recip. ohms.	
				Observed	Calculated
	133.84	956.5	22.4	934.1	925.4
Equation used) (lc)	66.92	521.5	13.2	508.3	529.6
	33.46	293.8	10.15	283.7	285.1
K ₀ = 405 × 10 ⁻⁴	8.365	85.64	10.85	74.79	75.69
	2.092	27.61	7.33	20.28	19.23
λ _s = 3748 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.5228	12.68	7.72	4.96	4.82

Variation of specific conductivity of azrehtic acid with dilution :

Kulshrestha⁶ has investigated the variation of specific conductivity with dilution of sols of azrehtic acid (A R A) in the presence of 0.0005N and 0.002N

sulphuric acid at 35°. The (A R A) extracted from the gum of the plant *Azadirachta Indica* (commonly known as Neem tree) has been purified by electro dialysis before use. His data⁶ are recorded in the Tables 3 and 4 in which C denotes the concentration of (A R A) in gram equivalents per liter and λ , λ_a , and λ_s have the same significance as stated already. The values of λ_s found by Kulshrestha⁶ at 35° of 0.0005N and 0.002N sulphuric acid solutions in water are 2.41×10^{-4} and 8.8×10^{-4} recip. ohms. respectively.

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF SPECIFIC CONDUCTIVITY WITH CONCENTRATION OF (A R A) IN 0.0005 N H₂SO₄

Miscellaneous	C × 10 ⁴	θ	Values of λ × 10 ⁴ in recip. ohms.	
			Observed	Calculated
Equation used(1b)	2.593	0.0071	2.51	2.50
	10.37	0.0276	2.77	2.77
K ₀ = 3.66 × 10 ⁻⁴	20.74	0.0536	3.09	3.12
	31.10	0.0783	3.42	3.44
λ _a = 13.2 × 10 ⁻⁴	41.50	0.1018	3.74	3.75
	51.87	0.124	4.03	4.05
λ _s = 2.41 × 10 ⁻⁴	62.20	0.145	4.26	4.32
	83.00	0.183	4.86	4.82
	103.70	0.221	5.42	5.33

TABLE 4—VARIATION OF SPECIFIC CONDUCTIVITY WITH CONCENTRATION OF (A R A) IN 0.002 N H₂SO₄

Miscellaneous	C × 10 ⁴	θ	Values of λ × 10 ⁴ in recip. ohms	
			Observed	Calculated
Equation used-(2b)	10.37	0.0276	8.91	8.90
	20.74	0.0536	9.05	9.03
K ₀ = 3.66 × 10 ⁻⁴	31.10	0.0783	9.23	9.20
	41.50	0.1018	9.43	9.39
λ _a = 2.6 × 10 ⁻⁴	51.87	0.124	9.67	9.61
	62.20	0.145	9.77	9.84
B = 3.6	83.00	0.183	10.43	10.34
	103.70	0.221	10.94	10.92

Discussion

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table 1 that the value of λ_s diminishes as the concentration C of the meta-dye decreases. It is also very small compared to λ_s and its highest value 32.6×10^{-6} is less than 1 per cent of λ_s which is equal to 3748×10^{-6} recip.

ohms. It may also be noted that λ_s remains constant over the entire range of concentration variation of the meta-dye from $145.7 \times 10^{-4}N$ to $0.284 \times 10^{-4}N$. The values of λ_m calculated by using equation (1c) agree well with those observed. If (λ_m) varies with the dilution of the meta-dye sol from 984.8×10^{-6} to 2.61×10^{-6} recip. ohms and its lowest value is appreciably smaller than the specific conductivity, about 3.6×10^{-6} recip. ohms, of the distilled water used for dilution.

The data recorded in Table 2 show that the values of K_0 and λ_s used in equation (1c) for the calculation of λ_m of the 4B dye are the same as those used for the meta-dye. The agreement between the observed and calculated values of λ_m of the 4B dye may be considered satisfactory for all the concentrations except $66.92 \times 10^{-4}N$ and $2.092 \times 10^{-4}N$. It may be that there occurred some errata in printing the aforesaid values of C. If it be supposed that the correct values of C are $62.96 \times 10^{-4}N$ and $2.209 \times 10^{-4}N$ instead of $66.92 \times 10^{-4}N$ and $2.092 \times 10^{-4}N$ respectively and calculations are made using these supposedly correct values of C then the calculated values of λ_m are found to be 502.5×10^{-6} and 20.24×10^{-6} which are quite close to the observed values 503.8×10^{-6} and 20.28×10^{-6} recip. ohms.

It may be pointed out that the value of λ_i recorded in Table 3 is the same as that of 0.0005N sulphuric acid

solution observed by Kulshrotha⁶. It is much smaller than λ_a and hence the term $\lambda_i B\theta^2$ in equation (2b) is small compared to the sum of the other terms and may be neglected without introducing serious error. Equation (2b) then assumes the same form as equation (1b). It will be noticed from the data recorded (in Table 3) that the values of λ calculated by using equation (1b) agree satisfactorily with those observed.

The value of λ_i recorded in Table 4 is the same as that of 0.002N sulphuric acid solution but it is much greater than λ_a and hence the term $\lambda_i B\theta^2$ cannot be neglected and so equation (2b) has to be used for the calculation of λ . It will be noticed that the values of λ thus calculated agree well with those observed.

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